

OPPORTUNITIES TO CREATE AND USE E-LEARNING RESOURCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENT WORK COMPETENCIES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the advantages of organizing students' independent work through electronic educational resources, the requirements for the electronic platform, the internal capabilities of the electronic platform, and the benefits and positive impact on the effectiveness of learning for both students and teachers.*

Keywords: *independent work, competence, competency, electronic platform, electronic educational resource.*

Observations show that organizing the educational process through the creation of electronic educational resources is more effective than traditional teaching methods. It is important to acknowledge the ability to deliver educational materials in various forms to students. Organizing education through electronic educational resources creates new opportunities for the educational process, and its improvement and development further expands the active participation of students in the educational process.

The use of information and communication technologies in the education system and scientific research in the field of electronic teaching tools has a history of over 30 years. During this period, educational computer systems designed to utilize the various capabilities of information and communication tools have been developed in the United States, Canada, England, France, Japan, and a number of other countries.

Since the 80s of the XX century, a new direction related to the informatization of teaching, the creation and implementation of intellectual teaching systems has been rapidly developing [1].

The initial web technologies were developed in 1989 by CERN employee Tim Berners-Li and a year later, the first web browser was created. In 1991, it was used for information exchange between scientific organizations and was soon introduced to the general public. The inventor provided instructions on using programs to work with the Internet and later presented a catalog of other sites.

The development and wide spread of electronic platforms created new didactic opportunities in the field of education. The main advantages of electronic platforms are observed in the process of using graphic possibilities of presenting information in teaching.

The use of computer capabilities in the educational process not only increases the speed of information transmission to the student and increases its understanding, but also plays an important role in developing such qualities as curiosity, career guidance, and creative thinking.

The advantages of teaching in electronic educational resources are the free choice of the educational subject by students, providing conditions for communication with the teacher, and the implementation of the educational process based on traditional, new information and telecommunication technologies, regardless of the student's location and time.

Electronic educational resources create opportunities for delivering the main volume of the material being studied to students, interactive communication of the teacher during the educational process, independent work of students in mastering the materials being studied, and assessing their knowledge and skills acquired during their studies.

All components related to the educational process (knowledge, skills, abilities, goals, content, teaching methods, tools, etc.) are implemented using Internet technology in electronic educational resources.

The general requirements for electronic educational resources (Figure 2.2) are as follows:

2.2-Figure Requirements for Electronic Educational Resources

1. General Requirements: The structure and content of electronic educational resources should correspond to the curriculum, promote scientific, problematic, demonstrative, conscious, and independent learning, take into account the latest achievements of science, technology, and technology, and ensure the systematic and sequential nature of learning, and develop students' critical thinking, memory, and other abilities.

2. Didactic Requirements: Adaptability, interactivity, computer visualization capabilities, development of students' intellectual abilities, thinking, and ability to make independent decisions in complex situations, formation of skills in information processing, ensuring the systematicity and functional relationship of presenting educational material, ensuring the completeness and continuity of teaching, and having a system of intellectual problem-solving and research tasks.

3. Methodological Requirements: Creation based on the interconnectedness of conceptual, figurative, and dynamic components of educational material presentation, providing educational material in the form of a higher-order structure, taking into account the logical interconnections between subjects, and providing students with educational material.

"The possibility of creating various types of control for step-by-step development, visualization of all calculations performed in an open system, and demonstration of the relationship of variable objects or processes."

4. Psychological Requirements: Presentation of educational material should not only be verbal but also correspond to the sensory and perceptual aspects of cognitive processes. It should take into account the characteristics of psychological processes like perception, attention, thinking, imagination, and memory. The content of educational material should consider the age and

background knowledge of learners and be aimed at developing both figurative and logical thinking. It should provide for visualization of learning and the perception of objects, their models, and schemes in a sensual and comprehensible way, taking into account their life experience.

5. Technical and Technological Requirements: It should be possible to use it both locally and in a networked environment. It should maximize the use of modern multimedia and telecommunication technologies. It should be reliable and stable in operation and compatible with various types of computers and similar devices. It should ensure effective and efficient use of resources.

6. Sanitary and Hygienic Requirements: It should meet the requirements for font type and size, background color, contrast between font and background, line spacing, and screen decoration [2].

When creating electronic educational resources, it is necessary to follow the following basic principles: modularity, completeness, demonstrability, branching, controllability, flexibility, computer support and collapsibility principles.

Electronic learning resources created for independent learning are a demonstration tool during independent work, a tool for independent learning in independent work sessions, a monitor of student mastery levels, and a provider of problems and exercises.

Electronic learning resources allow students to read information, listen to lectures, perform tasks intended for practical training, check their knowledge and, if necessary, supplement it, self-control, etc. can recommend.

E-learning resources include simulators, tasks for practical training, tasks for independent work, test tasks, and software that monitors the process of imparting knowledge and learning at the same time. In other words, the exercises that describe the main informative part of the educational subjects and are designed to strengthen the acquired knowledge are test technologies that provide an opportunity to evaluate the students' knowledge.

Electronic educational resources designed for the educational process should have the following capabilities[2]:

- information resources with educational content in subjects;
- training courses in various directions;
- provide feedback;
- help to quickly find the necessary information;
- consider the timing of multiple references to hypertext explanations;
- use of the computer's multimedia capabilities when displaying information on the screen;
- to be able to evaluate the knowledge of students in each section of the subject according to their level of mastery;
- creating the possibility of updating the educational information bases of the subject, etc.

E-learning methodical materials created for independent educational activities in e-learning resources work with the help of automated software tools. Automated learning materials recommend information on relevant topics to learners and monitor knowledge. Depending on the result of knowledge control, learners are recommended tasks of different levels of complexity. With the help of automated learning methods, students can improve their knowledge even without the help of a teacher [3].

The advantages of using electronic educational resources created on the basis of web technologies in the educational process are as follows[4].

- Deeper and more thorough understanding of the material presented in the learning process.

- Introduction of a new form of learning into the education system.
- Opportunity to reduce the time spent on learning in the classroom (time saving).
- Long-term retention of acquired knowledge by students and the possibility of applying it in practice.

- Reduced time for the formation of certain skills in students.
- Increased number of tasks performed in classes.
- The student becomes the subject of learning as a result of active computer control.
- The possibility of modeling and directly demonstrating processes that are difficult for students to observe and reason about.

Therefore, like all economically developed countries, our country is also conducting research in various fields to solve the problems of computerizing the learning process.

The main function of electronic educational resources is to ensure interaction between the teacher and the student in the learning process. A learning process organized without constant interaction between the teacher and students is ineffective. Distance learning, unlike traditional classroom learning, does not always yield the desired results. In traditional classroom learning, interaction between the teacher and students takes place in a single location and at a specific time within the classroom. In distance learning, this process is carried out through telecommunication tools and computer network technologies [5].

Special attention should be paid to the creation of electronic textbooks and virtual stands when organizing the process of independent work with the help of electronic educational resources. Organization of the educational process based on electronic educational resources created on the basis of web technologies and electronic or multimedia electronic textbooks, shows that it has several advantages compared to traditional teaching. They can include the following [6]:

- Facilitating the delivery of educational materials to students by the teacher;
- Providing students with the opportunity to independently study educational materials presented during the lesson;

- Achieving a higher level of student assimilation;
- The possibility of organizing visual virtual stands within textbooks on an electronic platform;

- The ability to organize independent work activities in an interesting way using video, audio, and animation tools;

- The possibility of using recommended educational materials in a public manner, i.e., using network technologies in one or several classrooms and groups;

- The ability to quickly modify the information collection of educational materials and introduce new information reserves;

- The creation of opportunities to switch to lecture materials while performing independent work;

- Assessment, monitoring, and control of students' individual knowledge, and others.

Applying learning materials with these capabilities to distance learning allows students to simultaneously view, read, hear, reflect on, and repeat learning materials. increases and creates opportunities to work independently. The application of information technologies to the

educational process, especially the use of multimedia tools, creates great opportunities to describe the educational process in a didactic way. [7].

Web technologies-based electronic educational resources are designed for distance learning, and educational materials help students in completing tasks in practical and independent learning activities, as well as preparing for tests and exams.

In recent years, the development of internet technologies has led to positive developments in the use of new sources for independent learning. The internet contains a large number of educational information resources. The main goal of each information resource base is to provide students with sufficient and interesting information in various fields of science and create conditions for their independent work.

Electronic educational resources created for the education system and the training systems within them are required to consist of at least three parts: teaching, exercises, and control.

The process of organizing independent work using electronic educational resources helps students not only hear but also visually perceive the knowledge they are acquiring, and contributes to a deeper understanding of the concepts, ideas, and content.

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